

Quality of life in Muslim patients after stoma surgery

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Abstract

Introduction: Stoma is a surgical creation of an opening in the abdomen involving parts of either the gastrointestinal or urinary tract. **Objectives of the study:** The aim of conducting this survey is to elucidate effect of stoma over QoL (Quality of life) in Muslim patients and its determinants with respect to religious patterns. **Material and methods:** This cross sectional study was conducted in Dalian Medical University and Leady Reading Hospital, Sargodha during March 2019 to March 2020. We include 100 patients with colostomy or ileostomy, permanent or temporary performed in department of General Surgery, in year 2019. The data was collected through questionnaire quality of life scale for Muslim stoma patients. The data was collected with the permission of ethical committee of hospital. All participants were recruited on a voluntary basis. **Results:** The data was collected from 100 patients. There were 88 males and 12 females. Majority of patients (n=85) had ileostomy while 15 patients had colostomy. All ileostomies were temporary loop ileostomies. Majority of colostomies were also loop colostomies except three cases of end colostomy for malignant disease. Majority (80 %) of stomas were due to infective causes, while 15 were for trauma and 10 due to malignant disease. Out of 15 stomas made for malignant disease, 3 were permanent stomas. Majority of older patients had permanent stoma. Majority of patients were married. **Conclusion:** It is concluded that holistic approach is required when counselling Muslim patients who require

stoma-forming surgery to improve their post-operative HRQoL and maintain their participation in religious and spiritual aspects of life.

Key words: Quality, life, stoma, religious

Introduction

Stoma is a surgical creation of an opening in the abdomen involving parts of either the gastrointestinal or urinary tract. Colostomy includes releasing dung from the digestive organ, ileostomy from the small digestive tract, while urostomy implies releasing pee through the careful opening¹. In spite of late advances in surgery, specifically the improvement of therapeutic careful strategies, development of stoma is still in some cases essential and at different occasions compulsory. Stoma gets a significant change physical appearance and real capacity and patients with stoma are tested with various personal satisfaction (QOL) issues².

Customarily, specialized subtleties were examined in incredible insight concerning stomas however effect of stoma on an individual's personal satisfaction was disregarded. As of late effect of stoma on personal satisfaction is as a rule progressively perceived and considered. Personal satisfaction is progressively turning into a significant result measure in surgery³. It is a multidimensional develop, speaking to a person's emotional impression of physical, social and mental prosperity, just as fulfilment with the harmony between illness control and antagonistic impacts of treatment. Various nonexclusive personal satisfaction scales are accessible to survey the effect of ailment on different parts of an individual's personal satisfaction (QoL). The SF-36 and QLQ frameworks measure QoL inside a scope of spaces, just as giving a general sign of QoL. The SF-36 is a conventional proportion of health status created in the USA and can be utilized to quantify health results of clinical interventions⁴.

Muslim patients report a fundamentally lower personal satisfaction and otherworldly well-being following stoma surgery when contrasted with non-Muslims. This fuses mental components, social detachment, underreporting of intricacies, sexual dysfunction (prompting breakdown of conjugal relations) and either have restricted or no capacity to perform strict practices⁵. Attention to Islamic practices among healthcare experts associated with stoma-forming surgery is restricted. This may ruin a fully-informed conversation before surgery. Healthcare experts get practically zero preparing about the intricate association between culture, religion, health, and healthcare conveyance, remembering the effect of a stoma for Muslims⁶. There is a hole in information on healthcare experts with respect to Islamic strict practices that can be influenced by stomas. There is also a lack of appropriate understanding by Muslim patients about religious rulings regarding a stoma⁷.

Objectives of the study

The aim of conducting this survey is to elucidate effect of stoma over Qol (Quality of life) in Muslim patients and its determinants with respect to religious patterns.

Material and methods

This cross sectional study was conducted in Dalian Medical University and Leady Reading Hospital, Sargodha during March 2019 to March 2020. We include 100 patients with colostomy or ileostomy, permanent or temporary performed in department of General Surgery, in year 2019. The data was collected through questionnaire quality of life scale for muslim stoma patients. The data was collected with the permission of ethical committee of hospital. All participants were recruited on a voluntary basis. They were assured that their refusal to participate would not affect the care they would receive from the hospital.

Data collection

The data was collected through quality of life questionnaire (QoL). This questionnaire consist of 6 parameters. This include social function, body image, stoma formation, financial concerns, skin irritation and religious parameter also. The questionnaire were translated in urdu language also so that everyone understand it. Patients asked to score QoL based on 10 patients likert scale where highest and lowest imply highest and lowest level of QoL.

Statistical analysis

The data was collected and analysed using SPSS version 19. All the values were expressed in mean and standard deviation.

Results

The data was collected from 100 patients. There were 88 males and 12 females. Greater part of patients (n=85) had ileostomy while 15 patients had colostomy. All ileostomies were impermanent circle ileostomies. Majority (80 %) of stomas were due to infective causes, while 15 were for trauma and 10 due to malignant disease. Out of 15 stomas made for malignant disease, 3 were permanent stomas. Majority of older patients had permanent stoma. Majority of patients were married.

Table 01: Participant of persons with permanent colostomy, according to social demographic characteristics.

Variables	Persons with stoma	
	n	%
<i>Age group</i>		
26–35	1	8.3
36–45	4	33.4
46–55	3	25.0
56–65	3	25.0
>65	1	8.3
Total	12	100
<i>Gender</i>		
Female	10	83.3
Male	2	16.7
Total	12	100
<i>Marital status</i>		
Married	11	91.7
Widower	1	8.3
Total	12	100
<i>Religion</i>		
Moslem	7	58.3
Protestant	5	41.7
Total	12	100
<i>Education</i>		
Senior high school	3	25.0
Junior high school	7	58.3
Elementary school	2	16.7
Total	12	100
<i>Employment</i>		
Employee	2	16.7
Farmer	5	41.7
Unemployed	5	41.7
Total	12	100
<i>Long has colostomy</i>		
<5 months	7	58.3
6–10 months	2	16.7
11–15 months	2	16.7
>16 months	1	8.3
Total	12	100

Table 02: QoL questionnaire for all selected patients of stoma

		social function	Body image	Stom a functi on	Financi al concern s	Skin irritati on	Religio us	Posts score
N	Valid	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
	Missin g	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		33.75	39.45	27.56	34.50	25.10	49.60	55.4900
Medi an		33.00	35.00	25.00	25.00	25.00	50.00	50.0000
Mod e		54	25 ^a	33	0 ^a	25	0	50.00
Std. Deviation		16.543	21.188	14.37 5	37.231	23.953	29.680	23.26896
Variance		273.662	448.93 7	206.6 48	1386.111	573.727	880.884	541.444
Range		67	80	67	100	100	100	100.00
Minimum		0	0	0	0	0	0	.00
Maximum		67	80	67	100	100	100	100.00

Discussion

Measurement of quality of life is necessary in order to determine the impact of a disease and its treatment on an individual's well-being. In the western side of the equator the majority of stoma developments are auxiliary to either dangerous sickness or provocative gut infection, so patients will in general score higher and report a superior personal satisfaction after surgery⁸. Kuz et al⁹ played out a review cross-sectional partner study that deliberate effect on public activity and work obligations between 178 Muslim patients who either went through abdomino perineal resection or self-restraint saving gut resections for essential rectal carcinoma. Public activity and duty to work duties was likewise demonstrated to be fundamentally influenced in

a negative way for the sphincter-sacrificing accomplice. The creators' inferred that these issues were probably going to be key drivers of mental dismalness in this confidence group¹⁰.

The score of strict prosperity is generally high close to the score of by and large QOL score in western populace. This was in opposition to our conviction because we speculated that because Muslim patients will lose their sentiment of successful cleanliness important to perform strict ceremonies (ghusal/shower and wudhoo/bathing), they may feel themselves frustrated¹¹. Unexpectedly, strict prosperity was protected with a measurably critical contrast to other health related QoL spaces. This might be somewhat because of powerful mental advising by the strict pioneers. It further emphasizes that probably Muslim religious leaders better counsel their followers about religious matters and they have greater influence and control over the followers than doctors, nurses and psychologists¹².

Muslim patients with stomas evade or decrease their support in congregational petitions because of a dread of apparent sub-par cleanliness and dread of spillage. Congregational petitions are of specific significance to Muslims as these are compensated by a factor of 27 in contrast with performing them independently. Cavdar et al announced fasting and every day petition were fundamentally diminished in most of Muslims with a stoma in contrast with their pre-stoma Islamic practices¹³. Their examination found that 87.9% and 74.2% of Muslim patients consistently asked and abstained preceding their stoma arrangement. This diminished to 53% and 43.9% after stoma arrangement.

A “feeling of uncleanliness” was cited by 71% as the main reason for reducing prayer frequency, while 79% of non-fasters described “fear of causing damage to the stoma” as the main reason for not participating in Ramadan fasting¹⁴⁻¹⁵.

Conclusion

It is concluded that holistic approach is required when counselling Muslim patients who require stoma-forming surgery to improve their post-operative HRQoL and maintain their participation in religious and spiritual aspects of life. It is important for patients, patients' family members and healthcare professionals to understand and appreciate the practical and religious implications of stoma care before Islamic guidance can be delivered.

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